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METHOD FOR APPLYING CULTURAL CHARACTERISTICS TO EMOTIONAL PRODUCT DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

Culture brings memories, emotions and inspirations in life, while the conversion process in design is critical in deciding the emotional strength of a cultural product. This study explored how cultural messages in the environment can be absorbed, converted and distilled into cultural characteristics design by the association method for emotion arousal with stimulate and concern was used to deepen the product emotions and arrive at an initial design concept. By going through the three stages of preparation, connection and design & development, the designer was guided to observe the resources and usage behavior in their surrounding environmental. This study proposed a design method by having the designer observe local characteristics before integrating cultural background and emotional characteristics into conceiving design. Finally, "simile" and "metaphor" were used as differential methods to convert the analyzed cultural emotions into product creativity in order to produce two design concepts. The application of this design method then was evaluated and recommendations were made.

Keywords: emotional design, culture, emotion arousal, creative thinking.

1 INTRODUCTION

Culture is born from our daily lives. It is the taste and lifestyle that has resulted from the accumulated and evolved behavioral experience and emotions derived from the conditions of our living environment. In this Age of Knowledge Economy, the relationship between culture and industry has become closer than ever. As the cultural and

creative industry has been included in the National Development Plan, it is clear that Taiwan's economic development is at an imminent turning point. In the past, a product's usability and user-friendliness were the primary concerns during the development of industrial design. In another words, designers would need to communicate to the product users on the product's user direction and its purpose through the product itself. Norman (1990) had pointed out that a user-friendly design will be the criteria for a product's competitiveness in the future. Designers need to pay attention to and consider the context in which the users will be using the product. It is an extremely inspiring point of view for the designers nowadays who are merely pursuing the new designs. Designers need to be able to observe the potential of a behavior. And through their interpretation, they need to rethink how to present a product that allows users to operate using their instincts via a form that the general public would understand intuitively. When a new vocabulary that corresponds to the behavior is interpreted at the most outer layer of a product, the design work will be added with a touch of fun and meaning so that the understanding gap between designer and user will be reduced to a minimum. Norman (2004) made the observation that contemporary products emphasize more on the emotional perspective, where focus is put upon the emotional design that is developed from the considerations of emotional connection that a product endows upon people as well as product's pleasurable enjoyment. Desmet (2010) pointed out that product emotion is constructed by "stimulate" and "concern". Only through the impeccable combination of "stimulate" and "concern" will the user's attention and choice be attracted. Teng &

Chuang (2010) also proposed, “emotional arousal ranked from ‘low arousal (calm)’ to ‘high stimulation (activated)’ , the emotional experience activated by the interaction between the user and the product. Stimulation of arousal may be controlled to activate different experience processes to design product experiences that emphasize emotional dimensions.” Under this background where sentimental products are in, designers are asked to express their individual style and show their sentimental side at the same time. Designers also need to discover the cultural characteristics of a city in order for them to emotionally communicate with the consumers. However, how shall designers go about integrating traditional cultural characteristics and emotions in a particular area and then apply the cultural characteristics in their designs? With this question in mind, this research will be presenting a case study on the traditional old streets of Nanchuang Township through analyses of the literature and the real cases of creation of cultural products. From this case study, designers’ methodologies in absorbing the cultural messages, transferring and extracting the information into their design elements will then be presented. Designers’ strategies in using similes and metaphors to transform product emotion to two actual design results will also be discussed.

2 LITERATURE DISCUSSION

2.1 CULTURAL CHARACTERISTIC AND CREATIVE PRODUCT

What is culture? From the perspective of Linguistics, Lindqvist (1989) believed that wen, the first word of the two that make up the word “culture” in Chinese, has the meanings of strokes, lines, floral patterns, beautiful decorations and dress-up. Later, the word became part of the elegance and civilization (wen-ming as in Chinese) as referred to in Chinese culture. On the other hand, hua(化) seems to be composed of two people. One is on the top and the other at the bottom, as if two people have blistered their feet and are lying on the ground, which gives the meaning of change. Wen-hua (文化, Chinese word for culture), in Continental’ s Concise English-Chinese Dictionary, is translated to mean manners, measures; culture; ploughing, cultivation; raising, feeding, breeding. Kuan (1995) believed that culture is a series of

material and spiritual activities used in the management of certain ways of survival and living. When the activities are reflected on an instrument, it becomes a process where humans are using design and manufacturing to reflect the status of their external and internal needs. Ho & Lin & Liu (1996) pointed out that cultural products are exactly a re-examination and reflection towards the cultural elements implicitly possessed by the instruments themselves. Through design, the cultural elements are endued with a brand new contemporary outlook. Satisfaction of the instruments’ spiritual level is also explored, which separates a cultural product from ordinary products. All developed countries have realized that the global economy has been transformed as we move from the Industrial Age to the Age of Knowledge Economy. There was even a trend of Economy of Aesthetics that developed in the early 21st century. During that wave, many leading businesses around the world were all devoted to the application of design for value creation. Specifically, experiential design and emotional design were used as the primary factors that would create top-selling products in the market. Lin (2007) believed that culture is a form of living, design is a kind of living taste, and creativity is an acknowledgement via emotion. Design is an activity of cultural creation, and its ultimate goal is in creating a living culture and building a humanistic living environment. Li & Ho (2009) even pointed out that culturally derived products have to exhibit the profound essence and humanistic emotion hidden within our cultural and artistic lives. Through culturally derived souvenirs, life, culture and memories of the past are extended. Besides practicality, the products that consumers are purchasing also possess product values that encompass the building of a scenario and the transmission of professional knowledge in culture and arts.

Brick Plan (as shown in Figure 1) by designer Rock Wong (2010) is a great example of re-discovering the beauty of materials. He observed that bricks are ubiquitous, from the Office of the President in Taipei to the Min-nan settlements in Kinmen. A distinctive brick culture that has been widely applied and used in large quantity has become a unique identifier of Taiwan. As old red brick walls become ever more rare, Wong had the idea of using red brick, this

commonly seen building material in Taiwan, for his creation. This piece of work has the following implication, “Maintain the disappearing memories of red bricks; let the terminal point of old brick walls turn into the starting point for new design; redefine this ordinary material; make use of the stone-carving craftsmanship and restore the decayed red brick walls by cutting and polishing them into a unique texture. And the distinctive aligning combination of the red bricks is also transformed into a contemporary abstract totem”. From the case study of this Brick Plan work, one can note that if from taking a single material from the environment, and the material texture can be exquisitely handled, unique cultural emotions can also be expressed implicitly in simple style such as the upward arcs seen on the roofs of traditional Chinese temples.

Figure 1: Creation of Brick Plan (designer: Wong, 2010).

2.2 PRODUCT EMOTION AT THE TIME OF PURCHASE

Demirblik (2003) used to discuss the pleasurable elements in product design from the perspective of human factors engineering. The research believed that products shall transmit positive emotions from their specific characteristics. Also, through these characteristics the corresponding emotions will be aroused. The emotional connections that this research has proposed to be produced from pleasurable products include: a safe mind, trustworthiness, pride, energy, satisfaction and other pleasurable emotions such as happiness, interests or dreams that influence product reviews. When consumers spot products that can make them happy, in a right place, it is believed that more consumption will result. On the other hand, Hine (2003) has pointed out it is common to see the word “spree” being added after the word “shopping”, and “spree” itself has the meaning of “wild party”. Therefore, popular culture has often viewed shopping as a kind of undisciplined, extravagant and selfish behavior.

Consumption is hidden with a kind of desire to be superior. Besides satisfying needs, products also have to allow consumers to escape from all of their routine matters. Hine further pointed out that consumption is also a type of ceremony. During the consumption process, consumers may relate the products to love, religion, sacrifice, devotion and other values. Through the shopping process, it is possible for consumers to bring home things that cannot be bought by money. He categorized shopping motives into the following nine items:

(1) Power: Use purchased goods to declare own power and prove own value; (2) Responsibility: Shopping can be a sign of taking care of others, especially to women; (3) Discovery: Trade between strangers and learn from the experience; (4) Self-expression: A good may play a role in a world where personal identification is unclear; (5) Lacking sense of security: Both sellers and consumers create an illusion of “I am lacking that part in my life” and thus fill their lives with fashion; (6) Attracting attention: Longing to have own desire be recognized and not be questioned; (7) Looking for belongingness: Building tasteful community groups with goods and going against mainstream thinking; (8) Celebration: Shopping endows Christmas and other holidays with a whole new meaning; (9) Convenience: Integration and entanglement between shopping and life.

2.3 HAKKA AND THE SYMBOLISM OF ITS PATTERNS

Nanchuang is one of Taiwan’s classic Hakka cultural living circles. Cheng Hui-mei (2006) indicated that Hakka people had started immigrating to Taiwan in waves after mid-Kang-qi of the Qing Dynasty (A.D.1690’s). Most of the Hakka people in Northern Taiwan settled in the three counties of Taoyuan, Hsinchu and Miaoli. Their cultivation in the Miaoli region started in the first year of Qianlong (A.D. 1736) and gradually flourished for the two dynasties of Jiaqing and Daoguang. Through the difficult period of Hakka’s immigration to Taiwan, their image as people of diligence, endurance, persistence and perseverance has become one of the enduring symbols of Hakka communities. In regards to the presentation of embroidery patterns on Hakka clothing, they have been using spoonerisms, metaphors as well as the transformation of folk heritage and customs to express their inner

anticipations. In the following, we are analyzing the symbolism of Hakka classic patterns through spoonerisms and metaphors.

(1) Spoonerism: Express individual expectation and desire through numerous drawings. Using the interactive combinations of various patterns, auspicious words are derived from spoonerisms. The most common patterns include the following: bat, chital, turtle and European Magpie forming the auspicious words of “fu-lu-shou-xi” (福、祿、壽、喜) (fortune, wealth, longevity, happiness); butterfly and the word dieh (耄, meaning 80 years old in Chinese) have the same pronunciation, thus butterfly also has the meaning of longevity; ji (戟, Chinese halberd) and chin (磬, a kind of Chinese percussion instrument) have the same pronunciation as the words in Chinese that mean “fortune and celebration”, and rooster and chin also have the same meanings; bat and bronze coin form the saying that translates to “fortune is right here” (money has the same pronunciation as “the front”); European Magpie and plum flower create the auspicious saying meaning jubilation; rooster and peony are “wealth and promotion”; peony and vase are “wealth and safety”. And there are many other more examples not included here.

(2) Metaphor: Using quiet metaphors to express state of mind and expectation. Hakka embroidery often uses various characteristics of animals and plants found in the nature. For example, plum, orchid, bamboo and chrysanthemum, these elegant and noble flowers of four reasons are used as metaphors for the characters of an honorable and noble gentleman. Enormous and beautiful peony symbolizes wealth; peacock and phoenix of bright and colorful feathers represent good fortune; and mythical crane and turtle are symbols of longevity. From the perspective of product design, Lin & Huang (2002) proposed that there are five methods for comparison design on a product’s actual application: metaphor, simile, allegory, metonymy and analogy. Amongst them, simile makes uses of “as” or “like” to make an explicit comparison between objects, i.e. a figure of speech that makes comparison in the form of “A is like B”. For example, when saying that the girl’s skin is as white as snow, “snow” is used directly for the description of the whiteness. The abovementioned method where the meaning is

explicitly and clearly indicated will be called a simile. On the other hand, a metaphor is a figure of speech where comparison is made as “A is B”. With respect to the words themselves, the comparison refers to a specific object. But from the meaning of the sentence, the comparison is referring to an object in a different category while expressing places where these two compared objects are similar. In regards to a product’s application of metaphor, it is referring to a specific similarity (e.g. form, color, attribute...) between the product and borrowed symbol. Thus, the symbol is used to interpret the product. However, since the relationship between the product and the symbol is relatively vague, the comparison method is called a metaphor.

3 DESIGN AND OBSERVATION TOOLS FOR CULTURAL EXPERIENCE

Jones (1970) believed that design is comprised of three stages: divergence, transformation and convergence. Amongst them, the most intriguing would be how to define the range of design’s expansion and control emotion’s characteristics while continuing onto the convergence stage. Zeisel (1984) believed that through tools for environment-behavior research, more in-depth analyses could be proposed to help with the designer’s creation. The paper also proposed that designers need to observe the behaviors that have already taken place, the space or the byproducts after the product has been used, e.g. wear, residual signs or signs of something missing. Wear shows the deterioration from long use, e.g. people create a small trail because they make a shortcut by passing over grass or the notch cut by a knife on a meat cutting board, etc. Based on related research and the synthesis of past design experience by the author of this research, this research is drafting a procedure for the observation and the design of cultural experience (refer to Chart 1) through the extension of Desmet’s (2010) point of view that product emotion is constructed by “stimulate” and “concern”. The procedure includes the following three stages: (1) Preparation Stage, (2) Transition Stage, and (3) Design Development. Each stage includes the two primary execution key points of “stimulate” and “concern”, which allows the procedure of design observation and development to be always monitored under the status of “stimulate”

and “concern”. A brief description of the procedure is provided below.

3.1 PREPARATION STAGE: PROCEED WITH OBSERVATION OF CULTURE IN THE ENVIRONMENT

(1) Observing behavior (“stimulate”): Designers need to observe the behaviors that have happened and are happening in the environment. Since an event is a type of procedural process (Norman, 1990), videotaping or follow-up description can be used to thoroughly describe the overall event procedure. Through observation of the environment, phenomena or issues can be found. During initial observation, personal judgment shall not be applied so to prevent the influence of biased opinion.

(2) Emotion experience (“concern”): Examine the emotions of the designer during field study. Observer’s impressions on the object-user relationship as well as his/her actual feelings towards object-object relationship are both recorded. Later, this series of personal experience and feelings are connected. And this “cultural impression” is also examined.

3.2 TRANSITION STAGE: DISCOVER WAYS OF INTERACTION BETWEEN AN EVENT AND A PERSON

(1) Finding out a cultural pattern (connect “stimulate”): Designers can record the physical characteristics of a material, including shape, structure, toughness and surface pattern. Secondly, designers can refer to people’s existing user habits,

e.g. finding a break spot during shopping, expressions, gestures and goods carried during dining, methods for displaying goods and products that attract consumers, etc. Through this exercise, designers will be able to find a starting point from where they will be able to establish the product’s characteristics and present the new design’s special features.

(2) Combination of the material images (express “concern”): Make use of the materials collected during trips or the materials in hand, and “re-manufacture” a cube that can express the experience this time around. In this way, the connecting relationships among surface, pattern, internal structure and style can be discussed. This study will limit the cube with a size of 20cmx20cmx20cm.

3.3 DESIGN DEVELOPMENT: MESSAGES SHOWING THE REPRESENTATION OF CULTURAL CHARACTERISTICS

(1) Obtain message regarding behavior awareness (express “stimulate”): Obtain and apply signs of related behavioral messages observed. Choose the expression method: Simile or metaphor is used for product creation. The design method of simile can directly make use of local colors or elements so to accentuate or exaggerate local flair. On the other hand, the method of metaphor initiates spectators’ connection of the scenarios and the feelings while they are using the products via an indirect or suggestive method (e.g. relaxation, freedom, group

3.1 Preparation Stage: Observation of culture in the environment		3.2 Transition Stage: Discover ways of interaction between an event and a person.	3.3 Design Development: Messages showing the representation of cultural characteristics.	
(1) Observe behavior (“stimulate”)→	(2) Emotion experience (“concern”)→	(1) Finding out a cultural pattern (connect “stimulate”)→ (2) Combination of the material images (express “concern”)→	(1) Obtain behavioral message (express “stimulate”)→	(2) Reinforce message and naming (interpret “concern”)→
Observe behaviors that have taken place as well as space or byproducts showing signs that product has been used.	Examine behaviors taking place. And then record feelings during the event.	Record physical traits of materials, and present product’s special features for the new design. ← Examine issues	Apply comparison and design method for the design process. ← Compare behaviors	Endow a name upon performance result and transformed design. ← Examine the compatibility level between design and the culture intended to deliver.

Table 1: Procedure of Observation and Design of Cultural Experience.

gathering, friendship, harmony, superiority, etc.) (2) Reinforce message and naming (interpret “concern”): designers can endow a name on the performance result or for the description of the user behavior for the transformation. In this way, reflection can be done on whether the design can be transmitted with the message it had hoped to deliver. Secondly, consideration shall be made in regards to the reminder effect naming may have upon users. When users are using this product under a specific scenario, appropriate naming can remind users of special memories or experience. As a result, it will be easier for the product to be accepted.

3.4 FORM A DESIGN TEAM

In this research, the author will be applying the observation and design procedure for cultural experience in Table 1 while instructing two college sophomores from the Department of Industrial Design (20 years old, female) during the observation and design of culture in the environment with the theme of “gift”. Considering their commute time, the two designers selected Nanchuang of Miaoli County as the location for their field study. The two designers had to plan a trip and finish collaborating on a “cube” 3D model within two weeks. Later, the two designers further proceeded on their own design process via simile or metaphor. And within six weeks, a total of two pieces of conceptual cultural products were created.

4 DESIGN RESULT

4.1 PREPARATION STAGE: OBSERVATION OF CULTURE IN THE ENVIRONMENT

Terrain in Nanchuang Township of Miaoli County, Taiwan is mostly made up of highlands and hills, with most of its settlements surrounded by mountains. The once-flourishing forestry and mining industry in old Nanchuang was severely damaged during a disastrous earthquake in 1935. At that time, a

Japanese team was asked to re-plan and re-design two-storey wooden Japanese-style buildings. A portion of the buildings are still now standing on the streets of Nanchuang. Highlights of the old street include the century-old Nanchuang post office, Nanchuang Theater Restaurant and others, which are mostly concentrated on Zhongzheng Road and Zhongshan Road. A relatively more famous scenic spot, Osmanthus Alley, is situated in a hidden alley, where the Nanchuang Community Work Studio displays event photos, community periodicals and local carving art pieces. Inside the alley, there are myriads of shops supplying local snacks and iced beverages, which have become places where tourists enjoy taking a break, have a chat or simply gather. “Clothes-Washing Pit”, a nearby tourist attraction spot, was once a traditional public washing location back in the days when local residents would lay out ten or so planks of clothes-washing stone slabs over the irrigation canal. The place was good for washing vegetables, fruits and clothing, and it has also become a social space where residents exchange information. Kangji Suspension Bridge, near the “Clothes-Washing Pit”, crosses over Zhonggang Creek and connects downtown Nanchuang and Nanjiang Village Old Street across the creek for a continual walking and recreation area that extends from Osmanthus Alley. The rich cultural ambiance here would make visitors feel as if they have traveled back in time. Nanchuang has developed into a famous tourist attraction. On weekends or holidays, the Old Street is filled with visitors who are here with a nostalgic or simple leisurely frame of mind. Side-by-side shops give a flourishing example of the old and the new of Nanchuang. However, there also exists amidst it all the commercial concern that the shops on the old street are selling overly similar products. Designers have summarized the photos of the buildings and the objects shot during their trip (as shown in Figure 2).

Figure 2: Impression of Nanchuang

Figure 3: Creation Transformed to "cube"

4.2 TRANSITION STAGE: DISCOVER WAYS OF INTERACTION BETWEEN AN EVENT AND A PERSON.

In this stage of "finding out a cultural pattern", the designers looked into the relationship between cultural impression and travel emotions of this trip. And they chose the architecture left behind from the Period of Japanese Rule, the unique scenery of the Clothes-Washing Pit and the application of contemporary composite materials to search for the cultural relationship between modern and historical times. Then, the process of "combination of the material images" was initiated through the techniques of cutting and decomposing, bringing wooden gutters, bricks, metallic tenon, polyester and cement to form a cube (as shown in Figure 3). The polyester-made parts in the cube allow osmanthus or sweet tea olive, a Nanchuang special, to be carried in the cube, as hints of the floral fragrance spread all over. Besides the volume and the exterior appearance, this piece of work is also possessed with an important point of view -the process of exploration and discovery. The story hidden within the volume also represents a complete journey. From the folk customs of the Hakka people and the traces that nature left behind, objects beyond our experience and knowledge were learned, and elements of designers' thoughts in regards to the

environment and the cultural images were also formed. Consequently, these all became the source of inspirational stimulants for the designers' creation of cultural products. In the following, the paper will briefly provide the two designer's key design results via the methods of simile and metaphor.

4.3 DESIGN DEVELOPMENT: MESSAGES SHOWING THE REPRESENTATION OF CULTURAL CHARACTERISTICS.

(1) METHOD OF SIMILE: FLORAL HARMONY DINING SET

Peony is a theme commonly seen in traditional Hakka fabric. The designer (Chun-Yi Wu) has also developed a dining gift set directly from this image. The gift set has a main body that is made of wooden materials, which is carried by a gloss-finish tray. The tray also allows users to see their own reflections while appreciating the product, which gives the fun attribute as if the user is taking out the dining set from a painting (Figure 4). When carrying the whole set together, user can take down the stabilizer on each side to be a chopstick rest. The dining set and the cup are placed together for easy portability. Continuing with the presentation of a "gloss finish", the cup is of a semicircle shape on its own and can be used alone. The two cups can also be taken down to form a perfect circle (Figure 5). This work

Figure 4: Floral Harmony dining set

Figure 5: Decomposable dining set (Designer: Chun-Yi Wu)

Figure 6: Easy-to-carry handle design

explicitly shows the “carrying” motion with its handle design, which gives a symbol of “bring me along” (Figure 6). Along with the traditional hand-painted floral patterns, the design hopes to touch every visitor with a warm image of “floral harmony”. Based on these concepts, a souvenir design that tells of the local pattern characteristics is born. This piece of work was showed at Taipei World Trade Center in, 2011.

(2)METHOD OF METAPHOR: HARMONY TEA (合茶) GIFT SET

Tea drinking culture is deeply rooted in Taiwan. When going out on a trip, especially to a place like Nanchuang with its rich culture, it will be wonderful if visitors can bring home an exquisite and collectible souvenir. Based on this, the designer (Shu-Ting Huang) finished the design via: decomposition, integration and hiding. The whole tea set brings together the concepts of packaging, including: tea pot, tea urn, tea cup and tea tray. From a more traditional and classic perspective, a cup set made of wood and porcelain is designed so that the user can easily taste the osmanthus brew (a seasoned sauce made of osmanthus and honey), a local specialty. The porcelain tea set can further accentuate the golden glow of osmanthus brewed tea. The idea for the product’s outer packaging came from decomposition. The bottom of the product has a rectangular foundation of symmetrical design perfectly made for a porcelain cup (as shown in Figure 7-8). On the sides, concave wooden blocks

along the bottom cover and embrace the whole tea set (this refers exactly refers to the hidden concept). The design of not completely enclosing the outer packaging and showing only a portion of the pot lid seem to be seducing people to discover its existence with the tiny clue for user to find it. The tea set is also arranged in a way resembling orderly-aligned shops standing side-by-side. The pot lid also serves as the central focus, from where circles of ripple-like gutters (as shown in Figure 9) spread outward to symbolize a tranquil Zen tea-appreciating ambiance. Through using the tea set to make cups of steaming hot tea, families and friends are brought together in parks and at home as they happily chat with each other while having their tea. It is an image that the tea set is hoping to deliver(合 with meaning of harmony & complete), a scenario where people can forget all the unpleasantness in their lives, put their earthly worries behind them and gather in harmony (Figure 10).The designer did not want to put extra decorations on the exterior and believed that the real excitement should happen after the user opens up the tea set. This piece of work participated in the 2011 Taiwan Young Designer Design Competition and won the nomination in the Crafts and Design category. It was also showed at the Taipei World Trade Center.

In the following, we summarize the considerations of cultural experience from crossed stimulation and concern that have gone into the design of these two projects in Figure 11.

Figure 7: Harmony Tea’s wooden rectangular gift box

Figure 8: The expanded tea cup set (Designer: Shu-Ting Huang)

Figure 9: Simulation in details

Figure 10: User scenario simulation of Complete Tea

Figure 11: Observation and Design Procedure & Points of Design Consideration of Cultural Experience

5 CONCLUSION

This research has observed, as a result of the process, that product emotion seems to gradually take its form during a journey. While getting to know an estranged town, the natural scenery and the humanistic and cultural characteristics along the way can reduce the uneasiness of a tourist. "I am not here to waste time nor waste money on unnecessary purchases", but "I want to bring this feeling back home and share it with my family." When expressing a specific local characteristic in a product design, it will be transformed into a record of the selection process and serve as proactive proof of a personal experience. Creation becomes an action that brings a journey to life and it also further rationalizes the integration of cultural characteristics and product design. By setting a procedure for the observation and the design of cultural experience, this research proposes the three stages of Preparation Stage, Transition Stage and Design Development, which include six execution key points. With the help of these elements, designers complete the phasic work of "cube" by converging all of the design emotions.

And through the two expression methods of simile and metaphor, two different styles of cultural products are developed. The procedure is meant to instantly help the designers take control of the emotion experience during observation and further transform it to emotional products of different features via the experience. The two conceptual designs completed during this research also need to consider target customer groups, market retail price, marketing, product manufacturing and related issues. If designers can continue exploring, with this research as the basis, it is believed that more rural townships will benefit as more products with local cultural characteristics are developed.

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